

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**AWARENESS AND KNOWLEDGE OF NURSING CARE IN
ENT DISORDERS IN PAKISTAN**Dr Iqra Ain Ali¹, Dr Hamna Malik², Dr Khadeeja Naz³¹Rawalpindi Medical University**Article Received:** October 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Introduction: Nurses play a pivotal role in providing qualitative healthcare services to patients, particularly in-patient care. **Objectives:** This study aimed to analyse the nursing care in ENT disorders in a tertiary care hospital of Pakistan. **Methodology of the study:** This cross-sectional study was done in Rawalpindi Medical University during March 2019 to November 2019. The data was collected through a questionnaire. The data was collected from those patients who visited the hospital for ENT disorders. The data collection team consists of ENT specialists, audiologists and hospital nurses. The hospital was well equipped with an operating microscope and ENT instruments. **Results:** The data was collected from 100 patients which were appropriate for our inclusion criteria. We observe all the symptoms that were commonly present in patients. So that we can identify the care related to these symptoms and problems of ENT. According to our results the group B which were handled with trained nurses for ENT nursing care were showed the better results as compared to group A who have less knowledge of nursing care. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that creating awareness of the common ENT conditions and how they are caused and treatment options available help decrease the burden of the disease in the community.

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Please cite this article in press Iqra Ain Ali et al, *Awareness And Knowledge Of Nursing Care In Ent Disorders In Pakistan*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Nurses play a pivotal role in providing qualitative healthcare services to patients, particularly inpatient care. Nurses are the only healthcare personals who are in close contact with the patients. Diseases of the ear, nose and throat (ENT) are universally a significant general health concern. The Global Burden of Disease (GBD), including ENT conditions, has consistently been accounted for to be relative to asset deprivation. Despite the fact that created nations are not exclude from the high ENT malady trouble, low pay African and Asian nations are generally influenced [1]. All around, incapacitating hearing misfortune influences around 466 million individuals, weakening individual sufferers, families and nations the same. Head and neck cancer, the ninth most normal harm, has high death rates in creating nations. In most of spots, people with correspondence troubles are not organized in health care frameworks as governments center around sparing lives rather than improving personal satisfaction [2].

Numerous patients with states of the ear, nose, and throat report a scope of various side effects and expectation their internist can recommend a cure that will lighten their wretchedness and cause them to feel better rapidly [3]. The most widely recognized ENT states of sinusitis, hearing misfortune, vertigo, and tinnitus can be assessed and treated in the essential care office, however indications of an intense or extreme condition should provoke a referral to a subspecialist, specialists concurred [4].

The most well-known issues justifying a visit to a specialist or a health care supplier in creating nations are related to ear nose and throat (ENT). ENT issues are the most widely recognized issues for which there are home solutions for medical treatments which are accessible, and most people deal with their concern in the network without looking for help [5]. What's more, because of the absence of authority experts right now, issues are treated by network rehearses. The investigations done have taken a gander at the commonness of ENT illnesses in kids and have indicated that the infection trouble is because of otitis media and its sequelae which are the most well-known reasons for preventable hearing misfortune in kids in creating nations [6].

Objectives:

This study aimed to analyses the nursing care in ENT disorders in a tertiary care hospital of Pakistan.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

This cross sectional study was done in Rawalpindi medical University during March 2019 to November 2019.

Inclusion criteria

All those patients who were suffered from any kind of ENT disorder were included in this study.

Exclusion criteria

Nursing staff involved in routine care of adult patients in general ward and special care units were included in the study whereas staff working in pediatrics, psychiatry, gynecology, intensive care and emergency units were excluded from the study.

Data collection

The data was collected through a questionnaire. The data was collected from those patients who visited the hospital for ENT disorders. The data collection team consist of ENT specialists, audiologists and hospital nurses. The hospital was well equipped with an operating microscope and ENT instruments. The hospital staff and nurses were taught about safe ear care practices, the harmful effects of prevalent traditional practices, and the treatment options available. They know how to identify the ENT disorders e.g. ear pain with or without discharge, sour throat, respiratory tract infection, throat pain, swelling, difficulty in eating and fever. The age range for this study was 10 to 50 years. Questionnaire method of data collection was used to know the prevalence of ENT-related conditions and analysing the nursing care in ENT disorders. This questionnaire include all the questions related to nursing care of ENT disorders.

All data were displayed in mean $\pm$ SD and analysed through SPSS 19.0 (IBM, USA). T-test and one-way ANOVA were applied for measuring comparison among groups. $P < 0.05$ was considered to have statistical meaning.

RESULTS:

The data was collected from 100 patients which were appropriate for our inclusion criteria. We observe all the symptoms that were commonly present in patients. So that we can identify the care related to these symptoms and problems of ENT. According to our results the group B which were handled with trained nurses for ENT nursing care were showed the better results as compared to group A who have less knowledge of nursing care. Subsequent to preparing, the mean score for the test in the gathering B expanded to 68%, demonstrating a measurably huge improvement from benchmark ($p < 0.001$). There was additionally upgrades in information for the individual modules, and appraisal and directing.

Table 1: Analysis of questionnaire of nursing care in ENT disorders

Module	Analysis of questionnaire		Significance
	Group A (Control)	Group B (After training group)	
Structure and function of the ear	56%	61%	<0.0001
Hearing impairment and deafness: causes and prevention	51%	53%	<0.0001
The outer ear: examine, treat and refer	52%	63%	<0.0001
The ear canal: examine, diagnose and clean	51%	67%	0.03
The middle ear: examine, diagnose and treat	50%	58%	0.28
Assessing hearing and counselling	62%	79%	0.17
All modules	48%	65%	<0.0001

Figure 1 ROC curve before training of nurses for care in E

DISCUSSION:

ENT ailments keep on pulling in little attention notwithstanding being a significant reason for dismalness and mortality around the world. Past examinations have consistently detailed under-resourced, understaffed and obsolete ENT, audiology and language instruction benefits in most of low pay nations [7-8]. With practically all the center ENT and supporting health staff situated in Lusaka city, the remainder of the nation's ENT administration is insignificant, and in numerous spots, non-existent. Therefore, emergency clinics offering ENT administrations are overpowered with patients as are numerous more significant level medical clinics in creating nations [9].

The enormous patient burden unavoidably prompts less medical experts and nursing staff, with quick consumption of the accessible assets. Thus, patient dreariness and mortality increments due to imperfect handling of medical and careful crises, poor nursing care, absence of basic care beds and careful blunder exuding from health specialist fatigue [10].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that creating awareness of the common ENT conditions and how they are caused and treatment options available help decrease the burden of the disease in the community. Utilizing prepared nursing care staff to spread the message of safe ENT rehearses, gives restoration of hearing misfortune through arrangement of hearing guides, and the assessment and careful administration by the pro (when seven days) helped the provincial network to get to the administration.

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